

METHODS OF ENHANCING SPEAKING SKILLS OF STUDENTS THROUGH STORY BASED LEARNING

Khoshimova Oydina Shuhrat qizi

Namangan Pedagogical Institute

Abstract:

This article discusses about which is the most effective methods of fostering students' speaking skills of students to learn observation skills to draft a story given in picture comprehension. Students will know how to attempt creative story writing based on pictures with comprehensive examples. Make a note of the common mistakes that students should avoid in order to excel at writing a story for picture composition.

Key words: *picture composition beginning phrases, illustrations, characters, EFL students, relevant content, interruption words, emotions of characters.*

Children love stories. Stories are magic, they can create other worlds, emotions, ideas and make the everyday seem incredible. They can teach us empathy and take us on terrific journeys. They can make us laugh, cry, jump with fright and then comfort us with a happy ending. From a very young age we learn how to enjoy a story both for pleasure and to help us make sense of the world and ourselves. In this article I'll look at why stories are important for EFL students and I'll share some simple story-based activities that can be adapted for different ages and abilities.

Story Writing Based on Pictures

In this learning concept, the students will learn the:

- Ways to make a story from pictures.
- Factors to consider while describing a picture.
- Acronyms help answer related questions easily.
- Story writing based on picture examples.

The picture composition has illustrations, examples and creative charts to make the topic exciting. Students can access the free worksheets that consist of story-making from pictures. These worksheets are available with their solutions in PDF format.

Definition

In a picture composition students observe the picture carefully to describe it or put it in the form of a story.

A picture can be a worth a thousand words and ideas as popularly said.

Picture 1

Q. Look at the above picture. Write a story about the day you went to the park on a family picnic. Use the picture as a reference for your composition.

Answer:

My family had decided to go on a picnic at a beautiful park. My father, mother, sister, and pet dog all left for the park early morning. We were excited to spend the time at the park. Since it is a little away from the city, we started our journey to the picnic spot early in the morning. We got a lot of food and toys. Once we got to the park, we selected a spot to place the mat. After we had got all our things, my father suggested we play with the Frisbee. My sister and I joined to play with him. We played football after that, and even our pet dog played with us. We had loads of fun. After a while, we ate a few sandwiches which mom had made. In the afternoon, we sat under a tree and rested for a while. In the evening, the tea and corn sellers passed by. We brought some corn and ate it happily. We ended our picnic before it got dark. It was a memorable day, and we enjoyed the entire day.

How to Write a Story from a Picture?

1. Observe the picture carefully to determine the basic theme. If the student is unable to understand the theme, it is advised to create a theme that is connected with the picture.

2. Try to structure the picture as per the elements of a story. Divide it into Introduction, body, and conclusion.

a. In the **introduction**, give a general theme of the picture with the setting or location.

Setting – Where and When a story takes place? You can also introduce the characters here.

b. The body of the story will include:

of the character and a little bit of imagination to give it a story touch.

Characters – Name the characters to lend a personal touch to the story.

Emotions – The general mood as per the picture and how emotions change as the story goes forward.

Conclusion

You can conclude the story by giving a resolution to a problem or giving a general emotion where the reader would feel happy at the end.

3. The full structure of the picture composition must be planned in mind before starting to write the same. Spread out ideas throughout the composition.

4. The ideas must be mentioned in a sequence and logically to make it an effective structure

Common Mistakes

1. Use the past tense when speaking about an experience in the past.

2. Ensure to include the three main parts of picture composition: An Introduction, the Body, and the Conclusion. All these three parts have to be separate paragraphs. Do not write all the parts in one paragraph.

Picture 2

Telling stories is typical in any language as we normally share about our past activities or experiences and what we observe. Since it is almost always part of conversations, storytelling is a skill that any person should get better at to communicate effectively and connect with other people. Learning how to tell your story in an organized and easy to understand way will help you to make your listener visualize what happened through your words. To guide you on how to effectively tell your story, follow the tips provided below.

Use beginning phrases to start a story

Although you may hear in some movies and books that telling stories are started with “once upon a time” this is not commonly used in real life. Beginning your story in this manner, makes your story sound fictional. In typical conversations, storytelling begins after being asked with a question “what happened?” Start by having an introduction to your story so your conversation partner will have an idea of what you are going to talk about. Use beginning phrases to cue your listeners that a story is about to be opened.

Beginning phrases that you can use are:

“It all started when...”

“To begin...”

“It all began when...”

Provide a background to set the scene of your story

Introduce to your listeners the setting of your story. By providing them a clear background, they will be able to imagine the scene of the story and feel as if they’re there. You can include details about who is involved, where it took place, and what you were doing at that time.

Talk about real events and challenges

One way of making your story relatable is by telling real events. Many are tempted to look good in their narrative and portray to be perfect, however, this can make your story less interesting. Some may find it boring, unrelated, and even sound boasting. Don’t strive to be perfect-looking in your stories but be honest and real. If you are going to talk about success or victories, refrain from omitting the challenges you faced along the way. People are interested in what’s relatable, and mentioning about struggles and how you overcome them is something that many can relate with. A story with a perfect life will sound unreal, and fictional. Hence when sharing real stories of real people or your personal story, do not try to invent a “perfect” character or plot nor create a story that you think your listener would prefer to hear.¹

¹ Pardede, P. (2010). Short stories use in language skills classes: Students’ interest and perception. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Seminar. Bringing Linguistics and Literature into EFL Classrooms* (pp. 1-17). Held in Salatiga, Indonesia, November 23-25, 2010, Satya Wacana Christian University

4. Choose relevant content

Include details that are important to be mentioned in the story and omit the ones that aren't needed. Overly detailed stories are hard to follow thus can create a rambling feel. You can share relevant content by involving details in your experience that you think are relatable to your listeners.

Use sequencing words

Continue giving details in the story in an organized way by including proper sequencing of events. As they hear the events occurred step by step, they can easily follow, link the details and visualize events chronologically. Smoothly transition your story from event to event by using sequencing words.

Sequencing words that you can use to continue or connect your story are:

"First of all..."

"Previously..."

"Next..."

"After that..."

"Finally..."

"In the end..."

Use interruption words to create suspense

While you are telling your story, you may want to add some elements to avoid the same flow in the story or make it even more interesting. To hint your listeners that something surprising or important is about to happen, use words that introduce interruptions. This will make your listener tune in and listen to you a bit more closely.

Interrupting phrases to add new elements in the story include:

Suddenly

Unexpectedly

People often listen to stories as part of engaging in a relaxing conversation or out of curiosity. Make sure to connect with your listeners and include details that are relevant to them. The content, the words that you use in your story, and how you deliver it will determine how it will impact others.

In Summary: Stories can...

- Enable children to empathise with unfamiliar people/places/situations.
- Offer insights into different traditions and values.
- Offer insights into universal life experiences.
- Help children consider new ideas.
- Reveal differences and commonalities of cultures around the world.
- Promote a feeling of well-being, fun and relaxation.
- Increase children's willingness to communicate thoughts and feelings.

- Encourage active participation.
- Increase verbal proficiency.
- Encourage use of imagination and creativity.
- Encourage cooperation between students.
- Enhance listening skills.

REFERENCES:

1. Pardede, P. (2010). Short stories use in language skills classes: Students' interest and perception. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Seminar. Bringing Linguistics and Literature into EFL Classrooms* (pp. 1-17). Held in Salatiga, Indonesia, November 23-25, 2010, Satya Wacana Christian University
2. Chalak, A., & Hajian, S. (2013). The role of storytelling aloud on the accuracy of pre-intermediate Iranian EFL students' spoken language in the classroom. *Journal of Faculty of Letters and Humanities*, 8(28).
3. Pardede, P. (2011): Using short stories to teach language skills. *Journal of English Teaching*,
4. Tien, T. B. (2013). Using short stories to improve speaking skill at pre-intermediate level. Retrieved January 24, 2018, from <https://123doc.org/document/3136407-using-short-stories-to-improve-speaking-skill-of-students-at-preintermediate-level.htm>